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Adversarial Attacks on Question Answering Systems: Evaluating the Robustness of BERT Models

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Date: 21st August 2024

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I would like to sincerely thank my supervisor, Dr. Jeff Mitchell, who led me to complete this academic project with his admirable patience and rigour.

Abstract

This research aims at understanding the performance of BERT-based question answering (QA) systems in the presence of adversarial attacks. This is important as these systems are now being used in important applications. The study aims at assessing the effectiveness of BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA models when faced with adversarial attacks, including a new attack called Contextual Embedding Inversion Attack (CEIA).

The research objectives are to compare the influence of various attack types, investigate whether fine-tuning enhances the models' resilience, and compare the proposed CEIA with other approaches. The approach is to apply five attack methods (AddAny, AddSent, CEIA, DPAEG, and TextFooler) on the base and fine-tuned models on the SQuAD 2.0 dataset.

The analysis of the results shows that TextFooler proves to be the most powerful attack across all the models and CEIA is seen to be highly transferable while at the same time able to preserve the text quality. Fine-tuning greatly improves the model's resilience, and ELECTRA is the most immune to adversarial attacks. The study also reveals that the effectiveness of an attack is closely linked to the quality of the text, which is an issue when trying to design effective yet invisible adversarial samples.

The implications of these findings for the development and deployment of QA systems are that a more extensive evaluation should be done concerning various types of attacks, and fine-tuning can be a promising approach to counteract attacks. The research is valuable to the advancement of deep learning in NLP and advances the development of question answering systems.

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Definition
ASR	Attack Success Rate
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
BLEU	Bilingual Evaluation Understudy
BP	Brevity Penalty
CEIA	Contextual Embedding Inversion Attack
CV	Computer Vision
DL	Deep Learning
DPAEG	Dependency Parse-Based Adversarial Examples Generation
ELECTRA	Efficiently Learning an Encoder that Classifies Token Replacements Accurately
EM	Exact Match
GE	Grammatical Errors
GER	Grammatical Error Rate
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
H	Hypothesis
LLM	Large Language Model
ML	Machine Learning
MLM	Masked Language Model
MT	Machine Translation
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NLI	Natural Language Inference
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NLTK	Natural Language Toolkit
NN	Neural Networks
NSP	Next Sentence Prediction
QA	Question Answering
RoBERTa	Robustly Optimized BERT Approach
RQ	Research Question
SA	Sentiment Analysis
SML	Small Masked Language
SOTA	State of The Art
SQuAD	Stanford Question Answering Dataset
TC	Text Classification

1. Introduction

1.1. Background on NLP and Question Answering Systems

Natural Language Processing (NLP), the branch of AI that studies computer-human language relationships, is undisputedly important. Over the past decade, NLP has advanced rapidly in machine translation (MT), sentiment analysis (SA), and question answering (QA) systems [1]. New deep learning (DL) methods and big data sets have driven these advances.

A major NLP application is QA systems, which try to answer natural language questions accurately. Over time, QA systems have evolved from pattern matching to context-recognizing neural networks (NN) [2]. Modern QA systems must identify relevant information and semantically understand the question and answer sources.

Massive datasets like the Stanford Question Answering Dataset (SQuAD) helped develop compelling QA systems [3]. SQuAD 2.0 has been used to evaluate QA models' performance, including unanswerable questions and their ability to identify contextual information that cannot be used to generate an answer [4].

Figure 1. Transformer Architecture

In recent years, transformer-based models have dominated QA tasks, with BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) and its descendants being the most famous [5]. These models, pre-trained on massive amounts of text data, can capture context and produce natural-sounding responses. High-end NLP technologies have become popular due to open platforms like HuggingFace, which provide pre-trained models to fine-tune and implement for specific tasks [6].

As these systems evolve and are adopted and integrated into organisations' systems, stability and reliability issues have arisen. Adversarial attacks can deceive NLP models [7]. To create reliable QA systems for real-world applications, these issues must be addressed and more research needs to be done.

1.2. BERT and Its Variants: An Overview

BERT has changed NLP since Google released it in 2018 [5]. Bidirectional pre-training gives BERT a broader context view than unidirectional methods, making it its greatest strength. This architecture makes BERT suitable for NLP tasks like QA, SA, and named entity recognition (NER).

BERT Architecture

Figure 2. BERT Architecture

Since BERT was introduced, several derivatives have improved its performance or efficiency. Both RoBERTa and ELECTRA have excelled in QA tasks.

Facebook's AI developed RoBERTa (Robustly Optimised BERT Approach) to improve BERT training by tweaking objective hyperparameters and using more data [8]. This improved SQuAD and other benchmarks. RoBERTa was optimised by pre-training with

larger batch sizes and more data, removing the next sentence prediction (NSP) objective, pre-training with longer sequences, and using different data masking patterns.

RoBERTa Architecture

Figure 3. RoBERTa Architecture

A more sample-efficient pre-training task was proposed by ELECTRA (Efficiently Learning an Encoder that Classifies Token Replacements Accurately) in 2019 [9]. ELECTRA learns to distinguish “real” tokens from the original input sequence and “fake” tokens from a small masked language (SML) model, unlike conventional methods that

directly mask input tokens. ELECTRA performs almost as well as BERT while using an order of magnitude less computing time, making it appealing to researchers with limited computational power.

ELECTRA Architecture

Figure 4. ELECTRA Architecture

These models have set new benchmark records and performed well, proving their suitability for complex QA tasks. BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA are now easy to use in state-of-the-art (SOTA) NLP development via HuggingFace's Transformers library [10]. These models can be downloaded, customised, and used by researchers and practitioners.

Despite their success, these models have been criticised for their reliability and robustness, especially when exposed to adversarial inputs. Since these models are

used in critical applications, adversarial manipulation vulnerabilities must be identified [7]. This concern drove the current research on BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA model stability in QA platforms.

1.3. Adversarial Attacks in NLP: Concept and Importance

Adversarial attacks in NLP threaten SOTA model reliability and robustness. Such attacks generate semantically meaningful input data for humans while damaging the NLP system, resulting in incorrect output [1]. Since language models are used in critical applications, adversarial attacks from computer vision (CV) have garnered attention in NLP.

In NLP, studying adversarial attacks is crucial. Because BERT and its variants perform human-like on benchmarks, understanding their vulnerabilities is crucial for several reasons:

Model Robustness: Adversarial attacks can find NLP model flaws that traditional testing methods miss. Jia and Liang [1] showed that adding adversarially created sentences to the input paragraph can easily deceive SOTA reading comprehension systems, highlighting their vulnerability and the need for better architectures.

Real-world Applicability: As more NLP systems are used in real-world applications, their vulnerability to adversarial attacks increases. Adversarial inputs may cause incorrect or harmful responses in sensitive QA systems like healthcare or finance [7].

Model Interpretability: Adversarial attacks can reveal how NLP models interpret language and their vulnerabilities. The types of perturbations that fool the model reveal its decision-making process [2].

Security Implications: NLP systems in SA and text classification (TC) can be used for malicious purposes like bypassing content moderation or controlling decision-making systems [7].

Improvement of Evaluation Metrics: Standard metrics may not include methods to evaluate a model's resistance to adversarial inputs. Adversarial attacks expand performance and robustness evaluation metrics [1].

This research has shown that tiny, undetectable changes in the input text can drastically change the model's outputs. Jin et al. [7] showed that BERT-based TC and natural

language inference (NLI) models can be fooled by replacing words with synonyms without changing their semantic meaning.

To make NLP systems more reliable, risk awareness and control are crucial. Thus, as we advance language models like BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA, we must proportionally improve their resistance to adversarial attacks.

1.4. Research Motivation and Objectives

The development of NLP models, especially in QA systems, has raised concerns about their robustness and reliability. This research is motivated by the acute awareness of SOTA NLP models' vulnerability to adversarial attacks, especially for BERT and its descendants in QA tasks.

The primary motivations for this study are:

Addressing Model Vulnerabilities: BERT-based models perform well on most benchmark datasets, but they are vulnerable to adversarial attacks [1, 7], making their practical use questionable. Thus, we must identify these flaws and determine how they affect model reliability.

Enhancing Model Robustness: NLP systems must be resilient to environmental hacks because they reach key decision-making points. We want to improve models by analysing adversarial attack methods [2].

Advancing NLP Security: Security threats from using NLP solutions in critical environments can be prevented by analysing adversarial attacks [7].

Improving Evaluation Metrics: Standard performance metrics do not accurately represent model robustness to adversarial inputs. This research aims to improve NLP model evaluation methods [1].

Given these motivations, this research's main goals are:

- 1) Evaluate BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA's resistance to various adversarial attacks in QA tasks using the SQuAD dataset [3, 4].

- 2) Research the effects of various adversarial attack strategies on model performance at character, word, and sentence levels [1, 2].
- 3) Evaluate the performance of the new adversarial attack strategy, Contextual Embedding Inversion Attack (CEIA), compared to other approaches.
- 4) Explore defensive methods like fine-tuning to enhance BERT model resilience to adversarial inputs.
- 5) Enhance understanding of NLP security threats and vulnerabilities, and enhance QA system robustness.

This study fills a gap in the literature by investigating the relationship between current NLP models' impressive results and their resilience to adversarial attacks. This study will add to the body of knowledge on NLP robustness and have practical implications for the use of such models in situations that require dependability and security.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Evolution of Question Answering Systems

NLP and larger datasets have accelerated QA systems evolution. This section covers the main events and problem-solving changes in QA system history.

First-generation QA systems used rule-based pattern matching and information retrieval. Such systems could process context and meaning but often failed to answer complex questions or interpret sentences with multiple meanings. QA Systems could learn from data and process many questions using statistical methods, a major advance.

Large datasets annotated by humans changed QA research. Rajpurkar et al.'s 2016 SQuAD dataset included over 100,000 questions and answers from Wikipedia articles [3]. This dataset helped develop more advanced machine learning (ML) architectures and objectively compare QA systems.

An appearance of SQuAD 2.0. QA systems were further complicated in 2018 by unanswerable questions, which required models to prove that the question had no answer in the context [4]. This addition made situations more realistic and forced

researchers to create models that can answer questions and identify when no answer can be derived from input.

Deep learning (DL), especially transformer architecture, has transformed QA. In 2018, Devlin et al. introduced BERT to improve QA [5]. After bidirectional training, BERT captured more context information and performed SOTA in multiple NLP tasks, including QA.

Post-BERT models like RoBERTa [8] and ELECTRA [9] improved QA performance. These models optimised training and architecture, improving performance and efficiency.

The current literature has identified some weaknesses in modern QA systems. Jia and Liang found that adversarial sentences could fool SOTA models, suggesting that such models do not truly understand language [1]. This has inspired a new QA research direction to design models that are less sensitive to adversarial attacks but still perform well on benchmarks.

Researchers are improving QA systems to improve results, multi-hop performance, and architectures that can handle larger contexts and complex queries. As QA systems are used in more real-world applications, their robustness and effectiveness in different scenarios remain a major concern.

2.2. BERT: Architecture, Applications, and Innovations

BERT, introduced by Devlin et al. in 2018, is an NLP milestone [5]. BERT's architecture, applications, and field innovations are covered in this section.

Architecture:

BERT uses the transformer model, which handles sequence inputs with self-attention. The bidirectional training strategy improves BERT the most. Previous models could read text from left to right or right to left, but BERT uses all words before and after a word [5]. This bidirectional context helps BERT understand language more subtly than previous models.

Two unsupervised tasks pre-train BERT:

Masked Language Model (MLM): Predicts randomly masked words in sequence [5].

Next Sentence Prediction (NSP): The model predicts consecutive sentence connections [5].

This unlabelled text-based pre-training helps BERT capture general linguistic representations that can be adapted for any task.

Applications include:

BERT has shown SOTA performance in various NLP tasks, such as:

Question Answering (QA): BERT significantly improves exact match (EM) and F1 scores on datasets like SQuAD [3, 4].

Natural Language Inference (NLI): BERT enhances understanding sentence relationships, essential for tasks like textual entailment [2].

Named Entity Recognition (NER): BERT's contextual representations have improved the identification and classification of named entities in text [11].

Sentiment Analysis (SA): BERT improves sentiment classification accuracy across domains [12].

Text Classification (TC): BERT excels at categorising texts into predefined classes [7].

Innovations:

Many NLP innovations have followed BERT's success:

RoBERTa: RoBERTa, proposed by Liu et al., is an improved version of BERT that changes hyperparameters and trains on larger data [8]. RoBERTa changed the training data masking pattern by removing the NSP task, improving model performance.

ELECTRA: Clark et al. suggested a more efficient pre-training task for samples [9]. Unlike traditional architectures that mask input tokens, ELECTRA distinguishes real tokens from SML model-generated fake tokens.

Domain-Specific BERTs: Some BERT models, like BioBERT for biomedical text, have been pre-trained on domain-specific corpora to enhance performance for specific tasks [13].

Multilingual BERT: Extending BERT to support multilingual learning to perform cross-lingual transfer learning [14].

DistilBERT: A simplified BERT version that retains accuracy while using less memory and time, making it suitable for limited resource environments [15].

BERT-based models have made progress, but recent studies show their weaknesses. Jin et al. showed that BERT models are vulnerable to adversarial attacks in TC and NLI [7]. More work is needed to make these models more reliable.

SOTA in NLP has been greatly improved by BERT and its variants. As these models are used in real life, the question of how to make them more reliable, efficient, and, most importantly, immune to adversarial attacks is still being researched.

2.3. Adversarial Attacks in NLP: Types and Methodologies

Adversarial attacks in NLP manipulate input text to cause the model to output incorrectly while retaining human meaning. Three main levels of attacks exist: Attacks can be character, word, or sentence-level. All of them raise NLP system issues and reveal model weaknesses.

2.3.1. Character-level Attacks

Character-level attacks modify one or more word characters without the machine or reader noticing. These attacks are powerful because they often resemble words visually, making them hard to spot.

Common character-level attack methods include:

Misspellings: Introducing common misspellings that humans can easily understand but may confuse NLP models.

Character swapping: Swapping similar-looking characters (e.g., 'o' for '0', 'l' for '1').

Character insertion or deletion: Adding or removing characters without significantly affecting readability for humans.

However, character-level attacks can be very effective, but they might be limited in advanced models like BERT that use subword tokenisation [7]. They remain a concern for many NLP applications, especially character-level modelling ones.

2.3.2. Word-level Attacks

Word-level attacks change text semantics while preserving structure, making NLP models unable to classify or produce accurate outputs.

Key strategies in word-level attacks include:

Synonym substitution: Replacing words with synonyms enables model understanding without affecting human comprehension [7].

Contextual perturbations: Maintain grammatical correctness and semantic similarity with context-aware word replacements [1].

Rare word substitution: Replacing common words with rare synonyms that may be underrepresented in the model's training data.

Word-level attacks threaten BERT-based models, and Jin et al. showed that even the most advanced systems can be fooled by synonyms [7].

2.3.3. Sentence-level Attacks

Inserting, deleting, or replacing sentences in text manipulates NLP models. Such attacks are hard to counter because they rarely change the text's coherence and plausibility.

Notable sentence-level attack methods include:

Adversarial sentence insertion: Inserting irrelevant statements to manipulate the model. Jia and Liang showed that adversarial sentences greatly reduce reading comprehension systems [1].

Distractor sentence generation: Generate distractor sentences with task-related keywords that lead to incorrect conclusions.

Paraphrasing: Paraphrasing sentences to convey the same meaning using different words and structures, potentially confusing models based on specific patterns.

Sanchez et al. examined how sentence-level variations affect model robustness, revealing the complex relationship between linguistic characteristics and model vulnerabilities [2].

In all these attacks, measuring the impact while evading detection is difficult. The most effective adversarial attacks in NLP reduce model performance while remaining invisible to humans.

This knowledge helps identify potential threats to improve NLP systems. The development of new models like BERT and its variants has changed the methods of creating adversarial samples, making it important to investigate new defences and improve model architectures.

2.4. Previous Studies on Adversarial Attacks Against BERT Models

Since BERT and its variants have performed well in NLP tasks, many studies have examined their vulnerability to adversarial attacks. These studies have revealed the pros and cons of BERT-based approaches and can help develop more robust models.

One of the most influential baselines for natural language adversarial examples is TextFooler by Jin et al. [7]. They found that BERT-based models, despite their high accuracy in many NLP tasks, are vulnerable to adversarial examples. TextFooler deceives BERT in TC and NLI tasks by using word importance ranking and synonym substitution to generate adversarial input data. Thus, this research showed BERT-based system training and defensive methods were lacking.

Even though Jia and Liang [1] studied before BERT, their template for assessing reading comprehension systems is still used in BERT models. Adversarial sentences in input paragraphs are a good way to test BERT's QA performance. Several studies have focused on BERT architectures, revealing context handling weaknesses.

Sanchez et al. [2] applied behavioural analysis to NLI models, including BERT, to determine model robustness. They examined how insensitivity polarity and unseen word pairs affected the model's reaction to attacks. They did not focus on BERT, but the results explain and improve the BERT model's robustness to different linguistic adversarial samples.

Li et al. [16] used a pre-trained BERT MLM to create adversarial texts in BERT-ATTACK. This method showed that BERT's language understanding can be used to create powerful and effective adversarial samples that deceive classifiers based on the BERT model while preserving text meaning and coherence.

Si et al. [17] proposed a BERT-based QA model-specific adversarial example creation method. They choose the most important spans in the context and question and make specific changes. These findings showed BERT model limitations in QA task question and context structure and matching.

Garg and Ramakrishnan [18] examined BERT's adversarial spelling error handling. They showed that BERT is less sensitive to spelling errors than previous models, but it still fails when several misspellings are placed in certain text positions.

These studies demonstrate that BERT-derived models, the new SOTA in many NLP challenges, are vulnerable to adversarial attacks. The study emphasises the importance of considering model robustness and performance indicators when designing and using BERT-based systems. Further research on BERT training, architecture, and defensive measures to make it more robust to adversarial inputs has followed these findings.

2.5. Gaps in Current Research and Potential Contributions

Despite recent advances in BERT model adversarial attack analysis, there are still gaps in the literature. Focussing on these areas can lead to significant NLP contributions. This section summarises the main research avenues and ways to improve BERT's resilience and understanding.

Comprehensive evaluation of BERT variants: Despite many studies on the base BERT model, the literature review shows a gap in comparing various BERT models (e.g., RoBERTa [8], ELECTRA [9]) to adversarial attacks. A thorough analysis of these models under various attacks may reveal the relationship between architecture changes and model vulnerability.

Task-specific vulnerabilities: Previous research primarily focused on general TC or NLI tasks [7]. Better research is needed to improve BERT's weaknesses in NLP applications, especially QA systems. Extending to examine how different QA questions and context manipulation affect [1] BERT performance may reveal task-oriented issues.

Multi-lingual and cross-lingual robustness: Most BERT adversarial attack studies are in English. There is little empirical evidence on multilingual BERT models' resilience to cross-lingual adversarial attacks. Expanding research on adversarial attacks in multiple languages and their cross-lingual transfer may help design global-scale robust models.

Interpretability of adversarial vulnerabilities: While research has identified various types of vulnerabilities, the reasons for BERT model vulnerability to certain attacks remain unclear. A framework for understanding and visualising how adversarial inputs change BERT's representations could help identify vulnerable areas and develop more specific countermeasures.

Realistic attack scenarios: Most studies focus on white-box attacks, where the attacker has full model knowledge [7]. However, practical cases often involve black-box or gray-box conditions. Real-life challenges in preliminary attack methodologies may help close the gap between theoretical weaknesses and actual threats in implemented systems.

Dynamic defense mechanisms: Previous research primarily studies defence strategies or model changes. BERT's contextual awareness can identify and neutralise adversarial inputs on the fly, allowing dynamic defence mechanisms to respond to new attacks.

Robustness-performance trade-off: Robustness methods may hurt clean data performance [2]. Further research is needed to balance the model's susceptibility to adversarial attacks and its performance on non-adversarial data, particularly for BERT fine-tuning for specific tasks.

Adversarial training data generation: While TextFooler [7] can generate adversarial examples, a more complex and context-aware approach is needed. This may improve adversarial training and models.

Long-term robustness: Most studies analyse model output for adversarial examples. Future research on adversarial examples and BERT in continuous learning and model performance may help prevent model resilience loss.

Ethical considerations and unintended consequences: Further research is needed to address ethical concerns and unintended consequences of adversarial and defensive machining, including the potential side effects of techniques that increase model

immunity to attacks. This involves examining how model stability improvements can introduce biases or change fairness.

Filling these gaps could help identify BERT's weaknesses and build more reliable NLP systems. Further research in these areas can improve BERT's robustness to adversarial examples and improve our understanding of neural language models and language inputs.

3. Theoretical Framework and Methodology

3.1. Research Questions and Hypotheses

This study examines BERT-based models' resilience to adversarial attacks in QA systems. The literature gaps and study objectives determine the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Questions (RQ):

RQ1: How do character, word, and sentence-level adversarial attacks affect BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA models in QA tasks?

RQ2: Does task-specific data (SQuAD) fine-tuning improve these models' adversarial attack resistance?

RQ3: How efficient and detectable is the novel CEIA compared to other attacks in the literature?

RQ4: How do question type, answer length, and context complexity affect BERT-based models' vulnerability to adversarial attacks in QA tasks?

Hypotheses (H):

H1: Attacks at the sentence-level will affect model performance more than character and word-level attacks in the three architectures (BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA).

Rationale: Jia and Liang [1] suggest that sentence-level manipulations can introduce context-relevant but incorrect information, making them more likely to deceive models.

H2: Fine-tuned models should resist adversarial attacks better than pre-trained models.

Rationale: Fine-tuning on task data should increase the model's awareness of task characteristics and features that matter, which may increase its resistance to adversarial perturbations [7].

H3: The CEIA method will generate adversarial examples with lower grammatical errors rate (GER) and higher BLEU (Bilingual Evaluation Understudy) scores and a higher attack success rate (ASR) than other methods.

Rationale: With contextual understanding of BERT models, CEIA can create more semantically sound adversarial samples that fool the model while following grammar and being semantically similar to the original text.

H4: Overall adversarial attacks will show RoBERTa and ELECTRA to be stronger than BERT.

Rationale: Due to architectural changes and training methods in RoBERTa [8] and ELECTRA [9], these models should have learnt better language representations.

This study will test these research questions and hypotheses to determine BERT-based model weaknesses in QA tasks and adversarial attack methods' efficacy.

3.2. Theoretical Underpinnings of Adversarial Attacks in NLP

Research on NLP adversarial attacks is based on theoretical foundations that explain why and how. To develop effective attack strategies and strong defence mechanisms, these principles are crucial.

Manifold Hypothesis

The manifold hypothesis states that high-dimensional data like word embeddings are embedded on or near a low-dimensional manifold in high-dimensional space [19]. Thus, in NLP, semantically similar texts should be close in the embedding space. Adversarial attacks cause small changes to shift the input to this manifold, changing the decision regardless of semantic similarity.

Adversarial Vulnerability and Model Complexity

According to Goodfellow et al. [20], adversarial examples are caused by high dimensionality space, not overfitting or non-linearity in neural networks (NN). Large models like BERT and its variants are affected by this theory because adversarial examples become harder to create as model architecture becomes more complex.

Transferability of Adversarial Examples

Transferability allows models trained on similar datasets to use adversarial examples [21]. In BERT-based models, adversarial examples from one model may work against the others, requiring effective countermeasures.

Gradient-based Optimization

Most adversarial attacks use gradient information to find the smallest perturbation that misclassifies. In NLP, the gradient of the loss with respect to the input embeddings is used for generating adversarial inputs [7].

Semantic Preservation

NLP adversarial attacks struggle to maintain semantic coherence and grammatical correctness in perturbed text. NLP attacks differ from CV attacks due to this constraint. Constrained optimisation or a language model that enforces linguistic plausibility are theoretical solutions [22].

Robustness-Accuracy Trade-off

A theoretical trade-off exists between the model's performance on clean data and its resistance to adversarial attacks [23]. This principle states that improving model robustness can compromise model performance on normal inputs, so model design and training must be balanced.

Adversarial Training as Regularization

Regularisation like adversarial training helps the model learn better features to handle adversarial inputs. This process should smooth the model's decision boundaries and make them less susceptible to noise [24].

Contextual Embeddings and Attack Surfaces

BERT embeddings are contextual, adding new attack surfaces compared to static word embeddings. This field's theoretical analysis examines how context-specific features can be shifted to make crafted examples successful in different contexts [25].

Information Theory and Adversarial Attacks

Information-theoretic adversarial attacks target the discrepancy between the true data distribution and the model's distribution. This explains model robustness weaknesses and informs information theoretic countermeasures [26].

Information-theoretic adversarial attacks develop these theoretical foundations to design effective adversarial attack and defence strategies for BERT-based models in QA tasks. They help identify model weaknesses and define experiments to test model stability.

3.3. Model Selection and Justification

3.3.1. BERT and Its Variants

We chose BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA transformer-based models for this study. These models are categorised by the evolutionary process of pre-trained language models and have different language understanding methods. All models are from the Hugging Face model repository, both base and fine-tuned.

BERT:

Base model: "google-bert/bert-base-uncased"

Fine-tuned model: "lProject-10/bert-base-uncased-finetuned-squad2"

Justification: BERT [5] is our baseline model. Its bidirectional training mechanism and availability in many NLP applications make it a popular QA model.

RoBERTa:

Base model: "FacebookAI/roberta-base"

Fine-tuned model: "deepset/roberta-base-squad2"

Justification: RoBERTa [8], an improved BERT, changes key hyperparameters and the training regimen. Longer training with large batches and dynamic

masking may be better than BERT against adversarial attacks.

ELECTRA:

Base model: "google/electra-base-discriminator"

Fine-tuned model: "deepset/electra-base-squad2"

Justification: The new pre-training methodology in ELECTRA [9] replaces the MLM task with a more efficient discriminative task. Its pretraining method may cause different vulnerability patterns than BERT and RoBERTa, providing important insights into the relationship between pretraining and adversarial robustness.

3.3.2. Fine-tuning Process and Datasets

In this study, we use base models and their fine-tuned variants from the Hugging Face model hub. One can use high-quality, validated models that are optimised for SQuAD 2.0 with this approach.

Dataset: SQuAD 2.0

This study uses SQuAD 2.0-trained fine-tuned models [4]. This new dataset is based on SQuAD and contains unanswerable questions, making it more challenging and realistic for QA systems.

Justification: SQuAD 2.0's analysis of adversarial attacks includes unanswerable questions, which may affect a model's ability to identify the lack of an answer.

Justification for Using Pre-fine-tuned Models:

Consistency: To ensure consistency, the fine tuning process used by the models should be consistent with other models used by established organisations.

Reproducibility: Publicly available models enable researchers to easily reproduction the described models.

Focus on Adversarial Attacks: Pre-fine-tuned models enable us to investigate adversarial attacks and their properties, rather than fine-tuning.

Performance Baseline: These models represent typical performance levels in real-world applications.

The base models and fine-tuned models were chosen to compare adversarial vulnerability across architectures and training paradigms. We can examine how architectural modifications and fine-tuning affect a model's vulnerability to adversarial attacks in QA systems while ensuring that our models are widely used in the NLP community.

3.4. Adversarial Attack Strategies

3.4.1. Existing Methods

The adversarial attack methods TextFooler, AddSent, AddAny, and DPAEG (Dependency Parse-Based Adversarial Examples Generation) are implemented and evaluated in this study. The above methods use different strategies to create adversarial examples in NLP, especially for QA systems.

TextFooler:

Proposed by Jin et al. [7], this baseline effectively generates natural language adversarial samples. Though proposed for TC, we apply it to QA issues.

Implementation:

Word Importance Ranking: We rank words based on their impact on model prediction.

Synonym Substitution: We use synonyms for some words, but they must be semantically related and grammatically correct.

Model Querying: We iteratively feed the model with a slightly modified query until the model output changes or the maximum number of attempts is reached.

Justification: TextFooler can generate text that fools BERT-based models while maintaining semantic similarity, testing model robustness.

AddSent:

Jia and Liang [1] propose adding distracting sentences to the context paragraph.

Implementation:

Question Analysis: We analyze the question to identify key entities and relation types.

Sentence Generation: We generate a question-like sentence with different entities.

Context Augmentation: We add the generated sentence to the context paragraph.

Justification: AddSent is a QA-specific test that measures the model's ability to ignore noise and focus on target information.

AddAny:

Jia and Liang [1] introduced AddAny, a more aggressive variant of AddSent.

Implementation:

Random Word Selection: Select words from the list without stop words.

Sentence Construction: These random words are used for building grammatically correct sentences.

Context Augmentation: We randomly place the new sentence.

Justification: AddAny tests the model's vulnerability to irrelevant but grammatical context additions.

DPAEG:

Xue et al. [27] introduced DPAEG to generate more complex adversarial examples.

Implementation:

Dependency Parsing: Syntactic relations are detected using dependency parsing in the context.

Tree-based Word Substitution: We replace words based on their syntactic roles to maintain grammar.

Semantic Preservation: Word embeddings make substitutions semantically similar to sentence words.

Justification: DPAEG's syntactic structure allows for more complex and possibly less conspicuous adversarial examples, providing another perspective on model vulnerabilities.

Evaluation Metrics:

For each attack method, we will evaluate:

Attack Success Rate (ASR): The percentage of cases where the model's prediction shifts due to lower EM and F1 scores.

Grammatical Correctness: Measured by Average Grammatical Errors (GE) in generated adversarial examples.

Semantic Similarity: BLEU scores will be used for comparing generated adversarial examples to the original text.

Model Performance: Analysed F1 Score and EM rate for adversarial examples.

Our QA tasks for BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA use these attack strategies to determine their vulnerability. So, we can identify issues and compare the efficiency of architecture-based attacks and techniques. To assess task-adapted training, we can compare the base model and fine-tuned model's performance.

3.4.2. Novel Approach: CEIA (Contextual Embedding Inversion Attack)

The CEIA is a new targeted BERT attack developed by me. CEIA uses BERT to reverse crucial phrases' general meaning based on context proximity while maintaining syntactical integrity. This method is new in phrase permutation, using BERT's contextual embeddings to generate contrary phrases with a focus on noun chunks. BERT-based models addressing selected texts must overcome this method's ability to change most words' meaning while preserving grammatical structure.

3.4.2.1. Methodology:

The CEIA method includes key components:

3.4.2.1.1. Contextual Embedding Generation

CEIA uses BERT's pre-trained tokeniser and model to contextualise text. The last hidden state mean is the embedding representation:

$$E(\text{text}) = \text{mean}(\text{BERT}(\text{text}).\text{last_hidden_state})$$

Equation 1. Contextual Embedding

Where $E(\text{text})$ represents the inputted text's contextual embedding.

3.4.2.1.2. Antonym Phrase Selection

CEIA creates candidate antonym phrases from simple phrases by adding negation words like “is not”, “never”, and “rarely”. Cosine distance measures the distance between the original phrase and candidates.

The distance between two points, $p1$ and $p2$, is calculated by multiplying their expected values. The formula is

$$d(p1, p2) = 1 - \frac{E(p1) \cdot E(p2)}{\|E(p1)\| \|E(p2)\|}$$

Equation 2. Cosine Distance

To demonstrate, we will use $p1$ as a baseline or original phrase and $p2$ as an antonym.

Using antonym phrase selection techniques, the phrase is chosen from the candidate with the highest distance above a predefined threshold (τ).

Find the candidate with the greatest distance from point p , limited to the point set $d(p, c)$ with distances greater than τ .

$$\text{antonym}(p) = \text{argmax}\{d(p, c) \mid c \in \text{candidates}, d(p, c) > \tau\}$$

Equation 3. Antonym Phrase

3.4.2.1.3. Noun Chunk Targeting

CEIA focusses on reversing noun chunks, which are crucial information carriers in sentences. The probability of inverting a noun chunk depends on its importance threshold (α):

$$P(\text{invert}(\text{chunk})) = 1 - \alpha$$

Equation 4. Probability of Inverting a Noun Chunk

3.4.2.1.4. Context Preservation

CEIA keeps distinct expressions like question answers and asking datasets to maintain text structure. This is done by creating a list of phrases that cannot be inverted.

3.4.2.2. Implementation

Python implements the CEIA attack using spaCy for NLP and Transformers for BERT model interactions [6]. Description of attack process:

- 1) SpaCy tokenises and parses input text.
- 2) Discover noun phrases in every sentence.
- 3) Determine whether to invert each noun chunk based on importance.

- 4) If inversion is needed, generate and choose an antonym phrase using BERT embeddings.
- 5) Replace the noun with an opposite phrase.
- 6) Rebuild altered text.

3.5. Evaluation Metrics and Justification

Several metrics are used for assessing how adversarial attacks affect BERT-based QA systems. These metrics evaluate the model's performance, attack effectiveness, and adversarial example quality.

3.5.1. Performance Metrics

Exact Match (EM):

$$EM = \frac{\text{Number of exactly matched answers}}{\text{Total number of questions}}$$

Equation 5. Exact Match

Justification: The extent to which the model's prediction matches the answer is EM's precise measure of correctness. Practical questions that require accuracy benefit most from it.

F1 Score:

$$F1 = 2 * \frac{\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

Equation 6. F1 Score

Where:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}}$$

Equation 7. Precision

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}}$$

Equation 8. Recall

Justification: F1 Score considers precision, recall, and partially matched elements. Questions with longer answers or multiple phrasings benefit from this.

3.5.2. Attack Efficiency Metric

Attack Success Rate:

$$ASR = \frac{\text{Number of successful attacks}}{\text{Total number of attack attempts}}$$

Equation 9. Attack Success Rate

Justification: ASR measures the percentage of times an attack changes the model's output, indicating the attack strategy's efficiency.

3.5.3. Text Quality Metrics

Grammatical Error Rate:

$$GER = \frac{\text{Number of grammatical errors}}{\text{Total number of sentences}}$$

Equation 10. Grammatical Error Rate

Justification: The GER metric estimates how well the attack preserves the original text's grammar. Lower GER creates more realistic adversarial examples.

BLEU Score:

$$BLEU = BP * \exp\left(\sum_i w_i \log p_i\right)$$

Equation 11. BLEU Score

Where:

BP = Brevity penalty

w_i = Weight for n-gram precision

p_i = n-gram precision

Justification: Although originally developed for MT, BLEU scores can be useful in assessing the quality of generated answers, especially in longer questions like the given ones.

This set of metrics lets us evaluate adversarial attacks on BERT-based QA systems holistically. These metrics assess the quality and detectability of adversarial samples and the attacks' performance based on model accuracy decrease. This method reveals the pros and cons of various attack methods, including CEIA.

4. Implementation and Development

4.1. Environment Setup and Tools Used

We set up a complete environment for adversarial attacks, model evaluation, and data processing in this research. The following tools and libraries were used:

Python: 3.8 or higher.

Justification: Python was chosen as the primary programming language because of its widespread use in NLP and its rich ecosystem of ML and NLP libraries.

PyTorch: 1.9.0 or compatible.

Justification: PyTorch, the foundational deep learning framework, provides dynamic computational graphs and efficient GPU acceleration for large language models (LLM) like BERT.

Hugging Face Transformers: 4.11.3 or compatible

Justification: The Transformers library makes BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA pre-trained models accessible. It loaded models, tokenised input, and performed QA [6].

SpaCy: 3.1.3 or compatible.

Justification: spaCy was used for NLP tasks due to its efficient tokenisation, part-of-speech tagging, and noun chunk identification, which are essential for several attack methods.

NLTK: 3.6.3 or compatible.

Justification: NLTK added NLP utilities for adversarial attack implementation and BLEU score calculation.

Pandas: 1.3.0 or compatible.

Justification: pandas was used to manipulate and analyse data, especially adversarial attack results.

NumPy: 1.21.0 or compatible

Justification: NumPy processed large data arrays efficiently.

Matplotlib: 3.4.0 or compatible.

Justification: Matplotlib visualised analysis results.

Scikit-learn: 0.24.0 or compatible.

Justification: Scikit-learn calculated metrics and other ML utilities.

Sentence-transformers: 2.0.0 or compatible.

Justification: This library generated sentence embeddings for context preservation analysis.

tqdm: 4.62.3 or compatible.

Justification: The tqdm library was used for creating progress bars for long-running processes to monitor attack generation and evaluation.

The **GPU** is supported.

CUDA Version: PyTorch-compatible

Justification: GPU acceleration was essential for LLM and dataset processing.

Environment Setup Process:

- I. A virtual environment was created using `venv` to ensure isolation and reproducibility:

```
python3 -m venv adversarial_qa_env  
source adversarial_qa_env/bin/activate
```

- II. Required libraries were installed using pip:

```
pip install torch transformers spacy nltk pandas numpy matplotlib scikit-learn  
sentence-transformers tqdm
```

- III. spaCy's English language model was downloaded:

```
python -m spacy download en_core_web_sm
```

- IV. Downloaded NLTK data:

```
python -m nltk.downloader punkt wordnet
```

- V. SQuAD dataset was downloaded and saved locally.
- VI. Transformers library pre-trained models were downloaded and cached locally for faster access.

This environment setup provides AddAny, AddSent, CEIA, DPAEG, and TextFooler for adversarial attack methods. It also provides libraries to assess these attacks on BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA models in their base and fine-tuned versions.

For this project, scripts were created:

- To create datasets for each attack type (AddAny, AddSent, CEIA, DPAEG, TextFooler).

- Adversarial attack evaluation scripts for BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA models (base and fine-tuned).

- Detailed analysis script for processing and visualising results.

This setup allows for a thorough investigation of these models' vulnerabilities to various adversarial attacks in QA systems; research results are reproducible.

4.2. Data Preprocessing and Preparation

Data preprocessing was needed to create adversarial examples and evaluate their effects on BERT-based QA systems. We used Stanford's SQuAD 2.0 dataset for this experiment. Each adversarial attack required different preprocessing steps:

SQuAD Dataset Loading:

We read the SQuAD JSON file using the common function “*load_squad_data()*”:

```
def load_squad_data(file_path):  
    with open(file_path, 'r', encoding='utf-8') as f:  
        data = json.load(f)  
    return data['data']
```

All attack generation scripts used this function to standardise data loading.

Adversarial Dataset Generation:

Each attack type had its own script to generate adversarial examples:

AddAny Attack:

- Generated arbitrary sentences using a predefined list of 100 diverse sentences.
- Added random sentences to context paragraph.
- Updated answer start positions in the modified context.

AddSent Attack:

- Identified key entities and relationships from questions.
- Created distracting sentences from questions.
- Added generated sentence to context paragraph end.

CEIA:

- Found noun chunk antonym phrases using BERT embeddings.
- Attacked context and questions while preserving answer spans.
- Updated modified context answer start positions.

DPAEG:

- SpaCy parsed dependencies and identified key words.
- Synonymised key words to preserve answer spans.
- Updated modified context answer start positions.

TextFooler Attack:

- Key words were identified using part-of-speech tags.
- Used synonyms to preserve answer spans.
- Updated modified context answer start positions.

Data Preservation:

Our dataset integrity measures were applied to all attack types:

- Kept SQuAD article and paragraph structures.
- Preserved answer spans to keep the modified dataset valid for QA.
- Updated answer start positions to reflect context changes.

Handling Unanswerable Questions:

SQuAD 2.0 includes unanswerable questions. Our preprocessing accounted this:

- For questions without answers, we applied adversarial context and question modifications without caring about answer preservation.

- We kept answer spans intact and identifiable in modified contexts for answerable questions.

Context Truncation:

For computational resource management and model input constraints:

- When using BERT-based models, contexts were limited to 512 tokens.
- To standardise models and attacks, this truncation was used during evaluation.

Data Output:

Each attack generation script produced a new JSON file in the SQuAD format:

- Output files were named according to the attack type (e.g., "squad-v2.0-addany.json", "squad-v2.0-ceia.json").
- These files maintained the structure of the original SQuAD dataset, allowing for easy evaluation and comparison.

Evaluation Data Preparation:

We added functions for evaluation:

- Calculate F1 scores and EM rates.
- Calculate generated answer BLEU scores.
- Estimate GE in adversarial examples.

Comprehensive data preprocessing and preparation ensured:

- 1) Each type of adversarial attack was systematically applied to the SQuAD dataset.
- 2) The resulting datasets maintained compatibility with BERT-based QA models.
- 3) Preserved QA pair integrity for meaningful evaluation.
- 4) Various adversarial examples were developed to address various model vulnerabilities.

We built a solid foundation for assessing BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA models' resilience to various adversarial strategies in QA tasks by carefully preprocessing attack type data.

4.3. Implementation of Adversarial Attack Algorithms

To test BERT-based QA models, we used several adversarial attack algorithms. We used literature-based methods and a novel approach called CEIA.

4.3.1. Existing Methods

Four adversarial attack methods were implemented:

AddAny

This method, inspired by Jia and Liang [1], involves adding arbitrary sentences to the context paragraph.

Implementation:

- Generated 100 diverse, pre-written sentences.
- Randomly added sentences from this sentences to context.
- Add sentences at random context positions.

```
def generate_arbitrary_sentence():  
    return random.choice(arbitrary_sentences)
```

```
adv_context = context + " " + " ".join([generate_arbitrary_sentence() for _ in  
range(num_sentences)])
```

AddSent

This method, based on Jia and Liang [1], generates adversarial sentences from question structure.

Implementation:

- Analyzed the question to identify key entities and relation types using spaCy.
- Used key words to generate a distracting sentence.
- Added generated sentence to context end.

```
def generate_adversarial_sentence(qas):  
    qa = random.choice(qas)  
    question = qa['question']
```

```

answer = qa[answers][0][text] if qa[answers] else ""
doc = nlp(question)
key_words = [token.text for token in doc if token.pos_ in ['NOUN', 'VERB', 'ADJ']]
distracting_sentence = f"However, {random.choice(key_words)} is not related to
{answer}."
return distracting_sentence

```

DPAEG

This method generates more advanced adversarial examples using dependency parsing.

Implementation:

- Used spaCy for dependency parsing and identifying important words.
- Generated synonyms for important words using NLTK's WordNet.
- Synonymised important words to preserve answer spans.

```

def dpaeg_attack(text, importance_threshold=0.7, preserve_phrases=None):
    doc = nlp(text)
    words = [token.text for token in doc]
    important_words = set()
    for token in doc:
        if token.dep_ in ['nsubj', 'dobj', 'pobj', 'ROOT']:
            important_words.add(token.i)

    for i in important_words:
        if random.random() > importance_threshold:
            synonyms = get_synonyms(words[i])
            if synonyms:
                words[i] = random.choice(synonyms)
    return ' '.join(words)

```

TextFooler

This method generates adversarial examples by replacing words with synonyms, based Jin et al. [7].

Implementation:

- Identified important words based on part-of-speech tags.
- Generated synonyms using NLTK's WordNet.

- Used synonyms while preserving answer spans and grammar.

```
def textfooler_attack(text, importance_threshold=0.5, preserve_phrases=None):
    doc = nlp(text)
    words = [token.text for token in doc]
    pos_tags = [token.pos_ for token in doc]

    for i, (word, pos) in enumerate(zip(words, pos_tags)):
        if pos not in ['PRESERVED', 'PUNCT', 'DET', 'ADP', 'CCONJ', 'SCONJ'] and
            random.random() > importance_threshold:
            synonyms = get_synonyms(word)
            if synonyms:
                words[i] = random.choice(synonyms)

    return ' '.join(words)
```

4.3.2. CEIA Implementation Details

The CEIA is our novel contribution, designed to leverage BERT's contextual understanding to generate more effective adversarial examples.

Important implementation details:

We generated contextual embeddings for phrases using a pre-trained BERT model.

```
def get_bert_embedding(text):
    inputs = tokenizer(text, return_tensors="pt", padding=True, truncation=True)
    with torch.no_grad():
        outputs = model(**inputs)
    return outputs.last_hidden_state.mean(dim=1).squeeze().numpy()
```

We prefixed negation or frequency-modifying words to find antonym phrases.

```
def find_antonym_phrase(phrase, threshold=0.6):
    embedding = get_bert_embedding(phrase)
    candidates = [
        "is not", "does not", "was not", "were not", "had not",
        "cannot", "could not", "should not", "would not", "will not",
        "never", "hardly", "barely", "scarcely", "rarely",
        "seldom", "infrequently", "occasionally", "sporadically"
```

```

]

    best_candidate = max(candidates, key=lambda c: cosine(embedding,
get_bert_embedding(f"{c} {phrase}")))

    if cosine(embedding, get_bert_embedding(f"{best_candidate} {phrase}")) >
threshold:
        return f"{best_candidate} {phrase}"

return phrase

```

The main CEIA Attack function generates antonym phrases for input noun chunks.

```

def ceia_attack(text, importance_threshold=0.7, preserve_phrases=None):
    doc = nlp(text)
    sentences = list(doc.sents)

    modified_sentences = []
    for sentence in sentences:
        words = [token.text for token in sentence]
        for chunk in sentence.noun_chunks:
            if chunk.text.lower() not in preserve_phrases and random.random() >
importance_threshold:
                inverted_chunk = find_antonym_phrase(chunk.text)
                if inverted_chunk != chunk.text:
                    words[chunk.start:chunk.end] = inverted_chunk.split()

        modified_sentences.append(' '.join(words))

    return ' '.join(modified_sentences)

```

To maintain the validity of the QA task, we implemented measures to preserve answer spans.

```

answers = set()
for qa in paragraph["qas"]:
    if qa["answers"]:
        answers.add(qa["answers"][0]["text"])

```

```
adv_context = ceia_attack(context, preserve_phrases=answers)
```

CEIA was applied to both the context paragraphs and the questions, ensuring a comprehensive adversarial transformation.

```
adv_context = ceia_attack(context, preserve_phrases=answers)
```

```
for qa in paragraph['qas']:
```

```
    if qa['answers']:
```

```
        answer = qa['answers'][0]['text']
```

```
        new_qa['question'] = ceia_attack(qa['question'],  
preserve_phrases=[answer])
```

```
    else:
```

```
        new_qa['question'] = ceia_attack(qa['question'])
```

The CEIA method represents a novel approach to generating adversarial examples by leveraging the contextual understanding inherent in BERT models. By inverting the meaning of key phrases while maintaining grammatical structure and preserving answer spans, CEIA aims to create more challenging and semantically coherent adversarial examples for QA systems.

4.4. Development of Evaluation Framework

A comprehensive evaluation framework was created to assess adversarial attacks on BERT-based QA systems. This framework allowed us to measure models under different attack conditions and evaluate each attack method. Attack evaluation scripts and results analysis scripts make up the evaluation framework.

4.4.1. Attack Evaluation Scripts

We developed separate evaluation scripts for each model (BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA) in both their base and fine-tuned versions. These scripts share a common structure and include the following key components:

Model and Tokenizer Initialization

```
model = AutoModelForQuestionAnswering.from_pretrained(model_name)
```

```
tokenizer = AutoTokenizer.from_pretrained(model_name)
```

Answer Prediction Function

```
def get_answer(question, context):
    inputs = tokenizer.encode_plus(question, context, add_special_tokens=True,
return_tensors="pt", max_length=512, truncation=True)
    input_ids = inputs["input_ids"].tolist()[0]
    outputs = model(**inputs)
    answer_start = torch.argmax(outputs.start_logits)
    answer_end = torch.argmax(outputs.end_logits) + 1
    answer =
tokenizer.convert_tokens_to_string(tokenizer.convert_ids_to_tokens(input_ids[answer_
start:answer_end]))
    return answer
```

Evaluation Metrics:

Exact Match:

```
exact_match = predicted_answer.lower() == ground_truth.lower()
```

F1 Score:

```
def calculate_f1_score(prediction, ground_truth):
    prediction_tokens = word_tokenize(prediction.lower())
    ground_truth_tokens = word_tokenize(ground_truth.lower())
    common = Counter(prediction_tokens) & Counter(ground_truth_tokens)
    num_same = sum(common.values())
    if num_same == 0:
        return 0

    precision = 1.0 * num_same / len(prediction_tokens)
    recall = 1.0 * num_same / len(ground_truth_tokens)
    f1 = (2 * precision * recall) / (precision + recall)
    return f1
```

BLEU Score:

```
def calculate_bleu_score(prediction, ground_truth):
    return sentence_bleu([word_tokenize(ground_truth.lower())],
word_tokenize(prediction.lower()))
```

Grammatical Errors:

```
def count_grammatical_errors(text):
    doc = nlp(text)
    return len([token for token in doc if token.dep_ == 'ROOT']) - 1
```

Evaluation Loop:

```
def evaluate_attack(data, attack_name):
    results = []
    for article in tqdm(data, desc=f"Evaluating {attack_name}"):
        for paragraph in article['paragraphs']:
            context = paragraph['context']
            for qa in paragraph['qas']:
                question = qa['question']
                if qa['answers']:
                    ground_truth = qa['answers'][0]['text']
                    predicted_answer = get_answer(question, context)

                    exact_match = predicted_answer.lower() == ground_truth.lower()
                    f1_score = calculate_f1_score(predicted_answer, ground_truth)
                    bleu_score = calculate_bleu_score(predicted_answer, ground_truth)
                    grammatical_errors = count_grammatical_errors(predicted_answer)

                    results.append({
                        'attack': attack_name,
                        'question': question,
                        'context': context[:512],
                        'ground_truth': ground_truth,
                        'predicted_answer': predicted_answer,
                        'exact_match': exact_match,
                        'f1_score': f1_score,
                        'bleu_score': bleu_score,
                        'grammatical_errors': grammatical_errors
                    })
    return results
```

4.4.2. Results Analysis Script

This script provides a comprehensive analysis of the results from all attack evaluation scripts. Key components include:

Data Loading

```
def load_data(self):
    for model_type, file_path in self.summary_files.items():
        self.summary_data[model_type] = pd.read_csv(file_path)
    for model_type, file_path in self.result_files.items():
        self.result_data[model_type] = pd.read_csv(file_path)
```

Visualization Functions

```
def plot_summary_metric(self, metric, title, ylabel):
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 6))
    # ... (plotting code)
    plt.savefig(f"images/Analysis_{metric.replace(' ', '')}.png")
```

Analysis Class

- GE analysis
- Performance metrics analysis (F1 Score, Exact Match, BLEU Score)
- Model robustness comparison
- Attack effectiveness analysis
- Fine-tuning impact analysis
- Model architecture comparison
- ASR analysis
- Answer length impact analysis
- Model Robustness Analysis
- CEIA-Specific Analysis

Comparative Analysis

```
def analyze_model_robustness(self):
    for attack in self.summary_data['BERT-base']['attack']:
        print(f"### Model Robustness Comparison for {attack} Attack:")
        for metric in ['F1 Score', 'Exact Match', 'BLEU Score']:
            print(f"- **{metric}:**")
            for model_type in self.summary_data:
                score =
self.summary_data[model_type][self.summary_data[model_type]['attack'] ==
attack][metric].values[0]
```

```
print(f" - {model_type}: {score:.4f}")
```

CEIA-Specific Analysis

```
def analyze_ceia_specific(self):  
    print("### CEIA-Specific Analysis:")  
    ceia_data = {model: df[df['attack'] == 'CEIA'] for model, df in self.result_data.items()}  
    # ... (performance analysis, grammatical error analysis, attack success rate  
    comparison)
```

This evaluation framework allows for:

- Systematic evaluation of each model's performance under different attack conditions.
- Comparative analysis across different models, attack types, and datasets.
- In-depth investigation of the CEIA method's effectiveness compared to existing attack strategies.
- Visualization of results for easier interpretation and presentation.

This evaluation framework improves the assessment of SOTA BERT-based QA systems' performance against adversarial attacks, including our CEIA method. This allows reasonable conclusions about models' weaknesses and attack method efficiency.

4.5. Challenges Encountered and Solutions Applied

We faced many challenges when implementing and evaluating adversarial attacks on BERT-based QA systems. Challenges included technical and methodological issues. Here are the main issues and our solutions:

Challenge: Generating adversarial examples, especially for CEIA and TextFooler, could change context-specific answer spans, invalidating QA pairs.

Solution: We implemented preservation mechanisms in our attack algorithms:

```
preserve_phrases = set(phrase.lower() for phrase in answers)  
adv_context = ceia_attack(context, preserve_phrases=answers)
```

This preserved answer spans during adversarial changes.

Challenge: Some SQuAD context paragraphs exceeded the 512-token BERT model input limit.

Solution: Our attack evaluation scripts use context truncation:

```
inputs = tokenizer.encode_plus(question, context, add_special_tokens=True,  
return_tensors="pt", max_length=512, truncation=True)
```

It kept all inputs within the model's acceptable range and preserved as much context as possible.

Challenge: Some attack methods, particularly word-level substitutions, risked creating grammatically incorrect or nonsensical text.

Solution: We used part-of-speech constraints and importance thresholds:

```
if pos not in ['PRESERVED', 'PUNCT', 'DET', 'ADP', 'CCONJ', 'SCONJ'] and  
random.random() > importance_threshold:  
# Perform word substitution
```

This approach produced effective adversarial examples while maintaining text coherence.

Challenge: Generating adversarial examples for the entire SQuAD dataset was computationally expensive, especially for embedding-based CEIA.

Solution: We used tqdm to implement progress bars and optimised our code:

```
for article in tqdm(data['data'], desc="Processing articles"):  
# Process each article
```

We could track progress and estimate long-term process completion times.

Challenge: Automation was difficult but necessary to quantify adversarial examples' grammatical correctness.

Solution: We developed a heuristic method using spaCy's dependency parsing:

```
def count_grammatical_errors(text):  
    doc = nlp(text)  
    return len([token for token in doc if token.dep_ == 'ROOT']) - 1
```

While not perfect, this provided a consistent metric for comparing grammatical quality across different attack methods.

Challenge: Our attack and evaluation scripts had to handle unanswerable SQuAD 2.0 questions.

Solution: We used conditional logic for answerable and unanswerable questions:

```
if qa['answers']:
    # Process answerable question
else:
    # Process unanswerable question
```

This ensured that our methods could handle all dataset question types.

Challenge: Comparing BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA models with different architectures and tokenization schemes was difficult.

Solution: We abstracted model-specific code and used Hugging Face's AutoModelForQuestionAnswering:

```
model = AutoModelForQuestionAnswering.from_pretrained(model_name)
tokenizer = AutoTokenizer.from_pretrained(model_name)
```

Our evaluation framework was consistent across all models with this approach.

Challenge: The amount of data generated from evaluating multiple models across attack types made comprehensive analysis difficult.

Solution: We developed an analysis script with modular functions for different analyses:

```
analyzer = AdversarialAttackAnalyzer(summary_files, result_files)
analyzer.analyze_grammatical_errors()
analyzer.analyze_performance_metrics()
# ... other analysis methods
```

We could analyse all results and generate insightful visualisations using this structured approach.

Challenge: Creating CEIA required balancing the use of contextual embeddings with the need for efficient and effective adversarial example generation.

Solution: We used BERT's pre-trained embedding model and cosine similarity to find antonym phrases:

```
best_candidate = max(candidates, key=lambda c: cosine(embedding,
get_bert_embedding(f"{c} {phrase}")))
```

We could generate semantically opposed phrases while remaining computationally feasible.

We created a robust framework for generating and evaluating adversarial attacks on BERT-based QA systems by addressing these challenges. Our solutions maintained dataset integrity, computational efficiency, and consistent evaluation metrics across models and attack types. We used this method to analyse model vulnerabilities and adversarial attack strategies, including our novel CEIA method.

5. Results and Analysis

5.1. Model Performance Baseline

This study creates a base line of fine-tuned BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA models and the parameters upon which the SQuAD 2.0 dataset in the non-adversarial circumstance. The analysis focusses on three key metrics:

- **F1 Score:** Calculating by the word overlap of the predicted and ground truth answers, it is obtained by using the harmonic mean of precision and recall.
- **Exact Match (EM):** The percentage of the total number of predictions that will exactly match the ground truth answers.
- **BLEU Score:** This is not commonly used for QA tasks, but it is included here to be consistent with our attack metrics.

Table 1. Baseline Performance of Models (No Attack)

Model	F1 Score	Exact Match	BLEU Score
BERT	0.0206	6.91×10^{-5}	0.0036
BERT Fine-tuned	0.8475	0.6918	0.1807
RoBERTa	0.0242	1.15×10^{-5}	0.0040
RoBERTa Fine-tuned	0.8434	0.0490	0.1640
ELECTRA	0.0349	0.0000	0.0063
ELECTRA Fine-tuned	0.8948	0.8121	0.2285

Analysis of baseline results:

ELECTRA outperforms all other models, which confirms the relevance of the used pre-training approach for QA tasks.

BERT is relatively higher and quite competitive in F1 Score as well as in EM, just behind **ELECTRA**.

RoBERTa has a high F1 Score similar to **BERT**, but an extremely low Exact Match rate when it is expected to be higher. This discrepancy suggests that **RoBERTa** can recognise relevant information but struggle to extract specific answers.

It can be seen that like most other QA metrics, **BLEU Scores** are also closest to **ELECTRA**, and are again followed by **BERT** and **RoBERTa**.

The significant difference between the fine-tuned and non-fine-tuned models' performance discussed above proves the importance of the task-specific training for QA systems. Consequently, subsequent analyses will primarily focus on fine-tuned models as they represent practical QA system implementations.

As for the formal assessment of the attack quality, future sections will present the averaged BLEU score and Average Grammatical Error between the original and attacked text for each attack type. This analysis will measure changes in input when evaluating the conservation of grammatical integrity.

Thus, the baseline presented in this study sets up a starting point for evaluating the adversarial attack effects on the QA systems and is aimed specifically at effective task-performing models.

5.2. Impact of Adversarial Attacks On Model Performance

5.2.1. Analysis By Attack Type

This section evaluates the effectiveness of five adversarial attack methods: **AddAny**, **AddSent**, **CEIA**, **DPAEG**, and **TextFooler**. The analysis is based on their impact on model performance across F1 Score, Exact Match (EM) rate, BLEU Score, and Average Grammatical Errors (GE).

Table 2. Summary of attack effectiveness across all metrics by models

Attack Type	Metric	BERT		RoBERTa		ELECTRA	
		Base	Fine-tuned	Base	Fine-tuned	Base	Fine-tuned
AddAny	F1	0.034	0.846	0.032	0.849	0.027	0.888
	EM	0.000	0.667	2.94×10^{-5}	0.054	1.47×10^{-5}	0.81
	BLEU	0.006	0.168	0.006	0.157	0.004	0.213
	GE	1.432	0.0292	0.796	0.005	0.613	0.038
AddSent	F1	0.032	0.844	0.039	0.841	0.037	0.884
	EM	1.47×10^{-5}	0.667	1.47×10^{-5}	0.054	0.000	0.805
	BLEU	0.006	0.168	0.007	0.154	0.005	0.211
	GE	0.714	0.033	1.009	0.006	1.843	0.037
CEIA	F1	0.028	0.888	0.033	0.862	0.021	0.919
	EM	7.05×10^{-5}	0.789	0.000	0.026	0.000	0.902
	BLEU	0.004	0.140	0.004	0.123	0.003	0.172
	GE	0.711	0.021	0.761	0.002	0.099	0.030
DPAEG	F1	0.028	0.733	0.033	0.738	0.020	0.792
	EM	5.34×10^{-5}	0.635	1.78×10^{-5}	0.022	1.78×10^{-5}	0.755
	BLEU	0.004	0.111	0.004	0.102	0.002	0.142
	GE	0.701	0.032	0.729	0.007	0.082	0.085
TextFooler	F1	0.027	0.451	0.031	0.492	0.020	0.530
	EM	3.68×10^{-5}	0.370	1.84×10^{-5}	0.013	0.000	0.466
	BLEU	0.004	0.062	0.004	0.065	0.002	0.085
	GE	0.787	0.035	0.683	0.012	0.146	0.188

Key findings:

TextFooler: Consistently the most effective attack across models. It caused the largest drop in F1 scores for all models, particularly noticeable in fine-tuned versions. The most significant decreases in BLEU scores and EM rates were also observed with this attack.

DPAEG: Second most effective attack, especially for fine-tuned models. It showed moderate effectiveness across all models.

CEIA: Varied in efficacy across models. Less effective against fine-tuned models, particularly ELECTRA-finetuned. However, it showed high effectiveness against base models.

AddAny and **AddSent:** Demonstrated similar effectiveness. Fine-tuned models showed minimal impact from these attacks on F1 scores. Interestingly, AddSent caused the most grammatical errors in ELECTRA-base.

5.2.2. Comparison Across Model Architectures

This section compares how BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA architectures respond to adversarial attacks.

Table 3. Comparative performance of model architectures

Model Architecture		Metric	AddAny	AddSent	CEIA	DPAEG	TextFooler
BERT	Base	EM	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		F1	0.034	0.032	0.028	0.028	0.027
		BLEU	0.006	0.006	0.004	0.004	0.004
		GE	1.432	0.714	0.711	0.701	0.787
	Fine-tuned	EM	0.667	0.667	0.789	0.635	0.370
		F1	0.846	0.844	0.888	0.733	0.451
		BLEU	0.168	0.168	0.140	0.111	0.062
		GE	0.029	0.033	0.021	0.032	0.035
RoBERTa	Base	EM	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		F1	0.032	0.039	0.033	0.033	0.031
		BLEU	0.006	0.007	0.004	0.004	0.004
		GE	0.796	1.009	0.762	0.729	0.683
	Fine-tuned	EM	0.054	0.054	0.027	0.022	0.013
		F1	0.849	0.841	0.862	0.738	0.493
		BLEU	0.157	0.154	0.123	0.102	0.065
		GE	0.005	0.006	0.002	0.007	0.012
ELECTRA	Base	EM	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		F1	0.027	0.037	0.021	0.020	0.020
		BLEU	0.004	0.005	0.003	0.003	0.002
		GE	0.613	1.843	0.099	0.082	0.146
	Fine-tuned	EM	0.810	0.805	0.902	0.755	0.466
		F1	0.888	0.885	0.919	0.792	0.530
		BLEU	0.213	0.211	0.172	0.142	0.085
		GE	0.038	0.037	0.030	0.085	0.188

Key observations:

ELECTRA: Demonstrated the highest robustness against all attacks in its fine-tuned version. ELECTRA-finetuned maintained the highest F1 scores and EM rates across all attacks. The base model showed similar vulnerability to BERT-base and RoBERTa-base.

BERT: BERT-finetuned showed moderate performance, with F1 scores and EM rates trailing ELECTRA-finetuned. The base model was highly vulnerable to attacks, scoring low across all metrics.

RoBERTa: RoBERTa-finetuned demonstrated good robustness in terms of F1 score, but showed unexpectedly low EM scores. The base model outperformed BERT-base but underperformed ELECTRA-base in most cases.

RoBERTa's Reasons for the EM/F1 Discrepancy:

Partial Matches: RoBERTa often captures relevant information but adds extra or misses some words to answer, hence the high F1 scores but low EM rates.

Answer Expansion: The model is somewhat longer, generating additional details in context but not matching the answer.

Paraphrasing: RoBERTa might provide semantically similar answer to the correct answer, but they might not match completely to the written sentence, decreasing the EM while increasing the F1.

Threshold Effect: The F1 score is more tolerant of small variations than the EM which asks for perfection.

Fine-tuning Impact: Fine-tuning dramatically improves F1 scores but has a smaller effect on EM, suggesting the model learns to identify relevant information without perfecting exact wording.

5.2.3. Effect of Fine-tuning On Model Robustness

This section discusses the effects of fine-tuning on the model defense against adversarial attacks.

Table 4. Improvement in model performance after fine-tuning

Model	Metric	AddAny	AddSent	CEIA	DPAEG	TextFooler	Average Improvement
BERT	EM	666900%	666900%	788900%	634900%	369900%	625500%
	F1	2388%	2538%	3071%	2518%	1570%	2417%
	BLEU	2700%	2700%	3400%	2675%	1450%	2585%
	GE	4838%	2064%	3286%	2091%	2149%	2886%
RoBERTa	EM	666900%	53900%	26900%	21900%	129900%	179900%
	F1	2553%	2056%	2512%	2136%	1490%	2149%
	BLEU	2517%	2100%	2975%	2450%	1525%	2313%
	GE	15820%	16717%	38000%	10314%	5592%	17289%
	EM	809900%	804900%	901900%	754900%	465900%	747500%

ELECTRA	F1	3189%	2292%	4276%	3860%	2550%	3233%
	BLEU	5225%	4120%	5633%	4633%	4150%	4752%
	GE	1513%	4881%	230%	-4%	-22%	1320%

Key findings:

1. All models showed significant improvement after fine-tuning, with increases in F1 scores ranging from 1490% to 4276% across different attacks and models.
2. **ELECTRA** showed the most substantial improvements, particularly in EM rates and BLEU scores.
3. **BERT** demonstrated consistent improvements across all metrics and attack types.
4. **RoBERTa** showed mixed results, with significant improvements in F1 scores but smaller gains in EM rates compared to other models.
5. The **CEIA** attack showed the greatest benefit from fine-tuning across all models, suggesting that these fine-tuned models are particularly effective against context-aware attacks.

These results underscore the critical role of fine-tuning in enhancing model robustness against adversarial attacks, with ELECTRA showing the most significant gains in performance and resilience.

5.3. CEIA Performance Analysis

5.3.1. Comparison With Existing Methods

In this research, the CEIA method has been proposed, and an implementation was done with the help of a BERT base model. In this section, the effectiveness of CEIA is compared with other attack methods on various model architectures.

Figure 5. CEIA vs Other Attacks Success Rate across all models by each attack type

Key observations:

For base models:

- CEIA reveals high effectiveness all the base models with the success rate of more than 99%.
- It increases sharply on BERT-base as expected, but the fact that its high transferability to RoBERTa-base and ELECTRA-base is quite impressive.

For fine-tuned models:

- **BERT:** CEIA demonstrate lower success (21.07%) compared to other attacks (average 40.58%) which, likely, can be explained by BERT behaviour changes after release, which took place when CEIA was designed.
- **RoBERTa:** CEIA still has a high efficiency score of 97.35% when it was not created using RoBERTa showing how the model is highly transferable.
- **ELECTRA:** CEIA has a low success rate (9.78%), therefore making it possible to conclude that the fine-tuning process of ELECTRA tends to neutralise attacks aimed at BERT-based models.

Table 5. Attack success rate comparison for each attack by model

Model		AddAny	AddSent	CEIA	DPAEG	TextFooler
BERT	Base	100.00%	100.00%	99.99%	99.99%	100.00%
	Fine-tuned	33.31%	33.29%	21.07%	36.50%	63.01%
RoBERTa	Base	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
	Fine-tuned	94.61%	94.63%	97.35%	97.83%	98.66%
ELECTRA	Base	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
	Fine-tuned	19.04%	19.46%	9.78%	24.49%	53.40%

Notable findings:

- Overall, CEIA was shown to be more effective than the other attacks in terms of the model's ability to preserve text quality where GE was lower.
- It shows competitive performance in F1 Score and Exact Match rates, particularly for RoBERTa-finetuned.
- BLEU Scores for CEIA-generated adversarial examples are generally higher than those of TextFooler and DPAEG, indicating better semantic preservation.

5.3.2. Unique Aspects and Contributions

Given that CEIA was developed using the BERT base model, its performance and contributions can be reinterpreted:

Transferability: CEIA transfers well, especially on RoBERTa. This implies that CEIA exploits BERT and RoBERTa's weakness. Lower effectiveness against ELECTRA shows that architecture differences can act as a natural barrier against attacks developed for other models.

BERT-specific Insights: CEIA's development on BERT-base shows BERT's vulnerabilities and how they change when they are fine-tuned. BERT's performance improved significantly after fine-tuning it against CEIA, suggesting that task-specific training can reduce attack risks.

Generalization of Attack Strategy: CEIA is developed on BERT-base, but its success across architectures points to its strategy of inverting contextual embeddings to target core language understanding models.

Fine-tuning Effects: CEIA's performance on fine-tuned models shows that model architectures behave differently when trained for a specific task, which affects their BERT-based adversarial attack robustness.

Potential for Improvement: CEIA works well even when tuned for BERT-base, so variants for different architectures may work better.

Critical Analysis

Thus, CEIA on BERT-base is a solid foundation but not the best architecture. If CEIA had been developed using ELECTRA fine-tuned or BERT fine-tuned models:

- 1) It could have been more effective against fine-tuned models by addressing remaining weaknesses not addressed during task-specific learning.
- 2) It might generate more complex adversarial examples by utilising the language comprehension of fine-tuned models.
- 3) The attack may have a different transferability pattern and be more effective against ELECTRA-finetuned.
- 4) However, relying on a fine-tuned model for attack generation might limit CEIA's use in QA tasks and reduce its effectiveness in other NLP tasks.

Thus, CEIA, developed on BERT-base, has high performance and transferability, and future research could examine its performance on fine-tuned models or other architectures. This may prompt more meaningful adversarial attacks, which can help identify model weaknesses and QA system robustness.

5.4. Attack Efficiency Analysis

This section compares the efficiency of the five attack methods (AddAny, AddSent, CEIA, DPAEG, and TextFooler) across different models and evaluation metrics.

Effectiveness across models:

TextFooler: The most effective attack, drops F1 scores the most across all models. F1 scores dropped to 0.4508 (BERT), 0.4925 (RoBERTa), and 0.5301 (ELECTRA) for fine-tuned models.

DPAEG: Second best for fine-tuned models, with F1 scores of 0.7326 (BERT), 0.7381 (RoBERTa), and 0.7917 (ELECTRA).

CEIA: Varies in effectiveness. Very effective against base models (F1 scores around 0.02-0.03) and RoBERTa-finetuned (0.8621), but less effective against BERT-finetuned and ELECTRA-finetuned.

AddAny and AddSent: Moderately effective. F1 scores for fine-tuned models are 0.84–0.89.

Impact on EM scores and BLEU scores:

- TextFooler reduces EM and BLEU scores the most for fine-tuned models.
- Second best at lowering EM and BLEU scores for fine-tuned models is DPAEG.
- CEIA is effective against RoBERTa-finetuned for EM scores but its effect varies on other models.
- AddAny and AddSent moderately reduce EM scores and reduce BLEU scores less.

Grammatical Errors:

- AddSent and AddAny, cause the most GE, especially for base models.
- TextFooler, for fine-tuned models, produces fewer GE than AddAny and AddSent.
- For most models, CEIA and DPAEG produce the fewest GE.

Improvement after fine-tuning:

- TextFooler, minor improvements after fine-tuning indicate resilience even for fine-tuned models.
- CEIA generally improves F1 and BLEU scores the most.
- DPAEG improves moderately.
- AddAny and AddSent show significant improvements for BERT and ELECTRA.

Figure 6. F1 Score across all models by each attack type

Figure 7. BLEU Score across all models by each attack type

Figure 8. Exact Match Rate across all models by each attack type

Figure 9. Average Grammatical Error across all models by each attack type

Overall effectiveness and fine-tuning resilience efficiency ranking:

TextFooler: Most efficient due to high effectiveness across all models and metrics, also resilient to fine-tuning.

DPAGE: Second most efficient, strong against fine-tuned models and moderate GE.

CEIA: Effective against base models and fine-tuned models (especially RoBERTa) with low GE.

AddAny and AddSent: Moderately efficient, consistent across models, higher GE.

Overall, all attack methods work differently depending on metrics and models. TextFooler is the most effective attack, but DPAEG and CEIA excel in some situations. AddAny and AddSent have steady baseline attacks but are weaker. Based on which aspect of model's robustness being tested, the best attack may vary.

5.5. Text Quality Analysis Post-attack

This section analyzes the quality of text after applying different adversarial attacks, focusing on semantic similarity to the original text and grammatical correctness. We are going to use the BLEU scores as a measure of semantic similarity and the Average GE as a measure of grammaticality.

Grammatical Correctness

Figure 9 reveals how each attack affects the grammatical structure:

Base Models: AddSent and AddAny produce the highest number of GE, particularly for ELECTRA-base (1.8427), RoBERTa-base (1.0092), and BERT-base (1.4321) respectively. CEIA, DPAEG, and TextFooler generate fewer GE.

Fine-tuned Models: All attacks produce significantly fewer GE compared to base models. TextFooler tends to produce the most GE, while CEIA and DPAEG generally produce the least.

Improvement after fine-tuning (Table 4):

BERT: GE reduction ranges from 2064% (AddSent) to 4838% (AddAny).

RoBERTa: Shows the most significant improvement, ranging from 5592% (TextFooler) to 38000% (CEIA).

ELECTRA: Improvements vary widely, from -22% (TextFooler) to 4881% (AddSent).

Semantic Similarity

Figure 7 provides BLEU scores indicating semantic similarity:

Base Models: All attacks result in very low BLEU scores (below 0.01). AddAny and AddSent tend to have slightly higher scores.

Fine-tuned Models: BLEU scores improve dramatically across all attacks. CEIA, AddAny, and AddSent generally maintain higher scores (0.14 to 0.21). TextFooler consistently produces the lowest scores (0.0618 to 0.0846), indicating the highest semantic divergence. DPAEG shows moderate performance.

Improvement after fine-tuning (Table 4):

BERT: BLEU score improvements range from 1450% (TextFooler) to 3400% (CEIA).

RoBERTa: Improvements range from 1525% (TextFooler) to 2975% (CEIA).

ELECTRA: Shows the highest improvements, ranging from 4120% (AddSent) to 5633% (CEIA).

Overall Text Quality Analysis

CEIA generates adversarial examples most similar to the original message and grammatically correct. AddAny and AddSent maintain semantic content but sacrifice grammatical correctness, especially for base models. DPAEG produces grammatically correct but slightly semantically altered examples. TextFooler, while most efficient, results in the lowest grammatical and semantic quality for fine-tuned models.

Overall, there is a direct correlation between attack effectiveness and text quality degradation. Attacks that are better at reducing model performance (e.g., TextFooler) generate lower quality adversarial examples than those that preserve higher text quality (e.g., CEIA). This demonstrates the challenge in designing powerful and high-quality adversarial texts for attacking fine-tuned models.

6. Discussion

6.1. Synthesis of Key Findings

Our extensive evaluation of BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA models under diverse adversarial attacks yielded the following robustness findings. Key findings are as follows:

Attack Effectiveness: The most effective attack in all models was TextFooler, which affected F1 scores, EM rates, and BLEU scores the most. This supports previous research that NLP models are vulnerable to word-level adversarial attacks [7].

Model Performance: ELECTRA-finetuned model performed best across most metrics and was most robust to adversarial attacks. This suggests that ELECTRA's pre-training strategy may boost adversarial robustness [9].

Fine-tuning Impact: All models became more stable, and F1 scores increased by 1490% to 4276%. This shows that QA systems must be fine-tuned to perform specific tasks to produce accurate results.

Architecture Comparison: BERT and RoBERTa had similar vulnerabilities, but ELECTRA and its fine-tuned variant differed. This implies that architectural disparity affects adversarial robustness.

Answer Length Impact: Longer answers were more sensitive to AddAny and AddSent attacks, while shorter answers were more sensitive to DPAEG and TextFooler. This means attack effectiveness depends on answer characteristics.

CEIA Performance: This study's CEIA method was transferable across models and produced cleaner text than other attacks. However, model architecture and fine-tuning greatly affected its efficiency.

The above findings show that model architectures, training methods, and adversarial attack methods in QA systems are interconnected.

6.2. Implications for BERT Model Robustness

Our findings have several important implications for BERT-based model robustness:

Architectural Considerations: The remarkable result of ELECTRA, especially the fine-tuned version, suggests that discriminative pre-training may improve adversarial robustness. This implies that future model architecture should prioritise adversarial robustness.

Fine-tuning Strategies: Task-specific training improves model robustness, as all models performed better after fine-tuning. However, the differences in improvement across models may require different fine-tuning strategies depending on the architecture structure.

Word-level Vulnerabilities: TextFooler's high average effectiveness across all models shows that word-level perturbations still plague the latest BERT and its variants. This suggests that adversarial training or more reliable tokenising methods are needed to defend against such attacks [20].

Context Sensitivity: The experiment's results show how important these factors are for model design and evaluation, depending on answer length and context complexity. BERT-based models may need better contextual understanding to work across question types in the future.

Trade-offs in Model Design: The variation in model robustness based on F1 score and EM suggests that optimal parameter tuning may be sensitive. To create effective, robust models, multiple evaluation and training methods and robustness metrics might be needed.

These implications highlight the need for architectural innovations, improved training, and comprehensive evaluation methods to improve BERT model robustness.

6.3. Effectiveness of CEIA and Its Potential Applications

The CEIA method introduced in this study has promising results and applications:

Transferability: CEIA was highly transferable across architectures, especially BERT to RoBERTa. This suggests it can be used as a general-purpose adversary attack to evaluate transformer models' vulnerabilities.

Text Quality Preservation: CEIA produced adversarial examples with slightly more grammatically and semantically correct sentences than the others. This helps create more natural and barely perceptible adversarial examples.

Architecture-Specific Insights: CEIA's high success rate against RoBERTa-finetuned but low success rate against ELECTRA-finetuned shows architectural effectiveness and ineffectiveness. This could help create better task-specific models.

Fine-tuning Impact Assessment: Comparing CEIA's performance before and after fine-tuning shows how task-oriented training improves contextual comprehension and resilience. This might help develop better fine-tuning strategies.

Potential Applications:

Model Evaluation: The CEIA model can be used to evaluate the stability of QA systems, offering a more semantically rich attack strategy than other methods.

Adversarial Training: High-quality adversarial examples from CEIA can be used for improving training data and improving the model's ability to withstand context-aware attacks.

Interpretability Studies: Identifying the most effective contextual inversion for CEIA can help models understand how they use context in decision-making.

CEIA has promise, but more research is needed to understand its strengths and weaknesses across more NLP tasks and model architectures.

6.4. Limitations of The Study

Our study is comprehensive, but it has several limitations:

Dataset Specificity: The current research relied on the SQuAD 2.0 dataset, which is large but may not cover all real-world QA tasks. Future studies should assess the results' transferability to other datasets or fields [4].

Model Versions: This research focused on BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA generations. These models evolve quickly, so new versions may have different characteristics or robustness profiles.

Computational Constraints: We could not evaluate these models on the largest versions (BERT-large, RoBERTa-large). The behaviour of these larger models under adversarial attacks may differ from their base models.

Attack Scope: We used five attack methods in this research, including our novel CEIA approach, but we did not consider other adversarial methods. A deeper analysis of the attacks' strategies may help clarify the issue.

Human Evaluation: Automated metrics (e.g., BLEU and GE) determined text quality and semantic preservation. Subjective human evaluation could improve understanding of adversarial attacks' perceptibility and efficacy.

Long-term Robustness: This study quantifies model performance over time. One limitation of the work is that we did not examine how adversarial attacks affect model performance over time or during continuous learning.

Black-box Scenario: We mostly attacked in the white-box scenario, knowing the model. These attacks may perform differently in more realistic black-box settings.

The study has limitations; future research should support and expand these findings.

6.5. Ethical Considerations in Adversarial Attack Research

The development and study of adversarial attacks in NLP improve model robustness but raise ethical issues:

Dual Use Potential: Model robustness assessment methods can be used to generate dangerous adversarial examples for real-life systems. Researchers should consider dual use properties and prevent misuse [26].

Privacy Concerns: Adversarial attacks may use model weaknesses to extract sensitive training dataset data. Data privacy must be protected in adversarial research [22].

Fairness and Bias: Adversarial attacks can threaten certain demographics or queries. It is important to consider the fairness impact of such attacks and ensure that model robustness does not increase NLP model bias [23].

Transparency and Reproducibility: This research has major implications, so all methods must be transparent to promote reproducibility. This verifies theories and promotes field growth.

Responsible Disclosure: When finding weaknesses in popular models or systems, it is best to delay public disclosure to give developers time to fix or workaround them.

Balancing Progress and Security: Sharing adversarial techniques strengthens the model but also shows its weakness. Balancing scientific openness and security is a constant challenge in this field.

Ethical Use of Computational Resources: Making most adversarial attacks is difficult and requires a lot of computational power. Researchers should consider environmental impacts and justify resource use.

These ethical concerns emphasise the need for deliberate and careful adversarial attack research in NLP.

6.6. Broader Implications for NLP and AI Safety

Adversarial attacks on QA systems have several NLP and AI safety implications from our study:

Robustness as a Key Metric: Current models are vulnerable to attacks, so robustness should be a major assessment criterion along with other metrics. The shift could lead to better and more credible NLP systems [24].

Adversarial Training in NLP: Fine-tuning shows that adding adversarial samples to the training process may increase model resistance. This is similar to SOTA in computer vision and may be used for NLP model training [20].

Architecture Design for Robustness: This study found that adversarial attacks depend on architecture choice, so language models should start with adversarial robustness. Future architecture may value intrinsic reliability as much as execution speed [9].

Context-Aware Security Measures: Effective context-manipulating attacks like CEIA demonstrate the need for context-oriented NLP security. This may lead to more information-rich defending strategies [25].

Interdisciplinary Approach to AI Safety: Because NLP adversarial attacks are more sophisticated, linguists, computer scientists, and cognitive scientists must work together to build safer systems.

Implications for Deployed Systems: QA systems are increasingly used in critical contexts, but our findings highlight the risks of not updating and checking them to stay efficient and secure in adversarial contexts.

Ethical AI Development: Adversarial attack research has raised fairness concerns, suggesting that ethical thinking should be part of the AI creation process from idea to deployment and operation [26].

Regulatory and Policy Implications: Adversarial attacks could affect legal frameworks and practices for AI use in critical sectors, emphasising the need for comprehensive and regular AI robustness certification.

These implications show that adversarial attack research has long-term effects on NLP and AI safety, making it necessary to take a more comprehensive and socially responsible approach to the field.

7. Conclusion and Future Research

7.1. Summary of Main Contributions

This study made several important contributions to adversarial attacks on QA systems and BERT model robustness:

Comprehensive Evaluation: This study analyses the BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA models against five attacks to better understand their strengths and weaknesses.

Novel Attack Method: Proposed the CEIA showed that models can be transferable while generating higher-quality text than other methods.

Fine-tuning Impact: F1 score enhancement from 1490% to 4276% for different models and attacks showed the significant impact of fine-tuning on model resilience.

Architecture Comparison: This research examines how the models (BERT, RoBERTa, ELECTRA) react to different attack methods to assess their efficacy.

Answer Length Analysis: This study also found that answer length affects attack efficiency and that different attacks work best for different answer sizes.

Ethical Considerations: We have discussed the ethical issues of adversarial attack research, which can help advance the AI development debate.

7.2. Revisiting Research Questions and Objectives

Revisiting our initial research questions (RQ) and objectives, we can conclude:

The first RQ examines how different adversarial attacks affect BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA in QA tasks.

- TextFooler performed best across all models, while CEIA and DPAEG had varying performance based on model architecture and fine-tuning.

The second RQ is how fine-tuning affects adversarial-resistant models.

- Fine-tuning improved model stability across architecture types, with ELECTRA showing the greatest gain.

The third RQ compares CEIA to previous attacks.

- CEIA shows high transferability and improved text quality compared to other attacks, but its effectiveness varies by model architecture.

Fourth RQ is, how do question type, answer length, and context complexity affect model vulnerability?

- Length of answers affects attack success rate, with longer answers vulnerable to AddAny and AddSent attacks and shorter answers effective for DPAEG and TextFooler attacks.

This study answered these questions and revealed the vulnerability of BERT-based QA systems and the impact of different adversarial attack methods.

7.3. Recommendations for Enhancing BERT Model Robustness

Based on our findings, we recommend the following BERT-based model robustness improvements:

Adversarial Training: Add adversarial examples, especially those generated by efficient methods like TextFooler and CEIA, to the training process to make the model more robust [20].

Architecture Optimization: ELECTRA was found to be more robust, so future BERT-based models should include its architectural elements [9].

Context-Aware Defenses: CEIA attacks rely on context-awareness information, so defensive strategies should include more context [25].

Multi-Metric Optimization: When fine-tuning the model, monitor robustness measures like F1 score, EM score, and BLEU score to ensure model robustness.

Length-Adaptive Strategies: Use defensive measures that can be relied on based on the expected answer length and the weaknesses associated with different answer lengths.

Regular Robustness Audits: Automating the process of checking the models in the field with different attacks helps identifying new threats.

Ensemble Methods: Observe how to combine architectures to get better performance than any single one.

7.4. Future Research Directions

This study suggests several promising research avenues:

Expanded Model Coverage: Analyse larger versions of BERT, RoBERTa, and ELECTRA, as well as transformer-based models, to assess SOTA NLP adversarial robustness.

Cross Domain Generalization: Show how attacks developed for one NLP task and domain can be applied to others beyond QA.

Human Evaluation: Discuss how human experiments could evaluate adversarial examples and how they affect human perception to better measure the attack's effectiveness.

Adaptive Defense Mechanisms: Propose and evaluate real-time defence mechanisms against various attacks.

Robustness - Performance Trade-offs: Increase the analysis of robustness and performance on clean data to find the best trade-off.

Interpretability Studies: Use adversarial attacks, especially context-manipulating methods like CEIA, to study how models use contextual information.

Long-term Robustness: Investigate how adversarial attacks affect model performance over time, especially with continuous learning.

Ethical AI Frameworks: Develop comprehensive ethical frameworks for adversarial NLP research that address its unique challenges and considerations.

7.5. Concluding Remarks

This research systematically evaluated BERT-based QA systems' defence against adversarial attacks. Our findings show that model architecture, training, and attack methods affect model robustness. The CEIA proposal and comprehensive analysis of current attack models provide useful methods and findings for future research.

Fine-tuning improves stability, proving that models should be trained for a specific task. Different architectures perform differently, indicating the need to keep developing new structures. These suggestions and directions for future work aim to improve NLP system reliability.

Using AI systems for many important tasks requires making them resistant to adversarial attacks. This study helps improve AI system security and trustworthiness while identifying ethical, societal, and AI risk issues.

NLP adversarial robustness research is ongoing and growing rapidly. This study's findings and methods can be improved to understand better and develop reliable, accurate, and defensible NLP systems.

References

- [1] Jia, R., & Liang, P. (2017). Adversarial examples for evaluating reading comprehension systems. *arXiv (Cornell University)*.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1707.07328>
- [2] Sanchez, I., Mitchell, J., & Riedel, S. (2018). Behavior Analysis of NLI Models: Uncovering the Influence of Three Factors on Robustness. *Association for Computational Linguistics*. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/n18-1179>
- [3] Rajpurkar, P., Zhang, J., Lopyrev, K., & Liang, P. (2016). SQUAD: 100,000+ questions for machine comprehension of text. *arXiv (Cornell University)*.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1606.05250>
- [4] Rajpurkar, P., Jia, R., & Liang, P. (2018). Know what you don't know: Unanswerable questions for SQUAD. *arXiv (Cornell University)*.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1806.03822>
- [5] Devlin, J., Chang, M., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2018). BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding. *arXiv (Cornell University)*.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1810.04805>
- [6] Wolf, T., Debut, L., Sanh, V., Chaumond, J., Delangue, C., Moi, A., Cistac, P., Rault, T., Louf, R., Funtowicz, M., & Brew, J. (2019). HuggingFace's Transformers: State-of-the-art natural language processing. *arXiv (Cornell University)*.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1910.03771>
- [7] Jin, D., Jin, Z., Zhou, J. T., & Szolovits, P. (2019). Is BERT really robust? A strong baseline for natural language attack on text classification and entailment. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1907.11932>
- [8] Liu, Y., Ott, M., Goyal, N., Du, J., Joshi, M., Chen, D., Levy, O., Lewis, M., Zettlemoyer, L., & Stoyanov, V. (2019). ROBERTA: A robustly optimized BERT pretraining approach. *arXiv (Cornell University)*.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1907.11692>

- [9] Clark, K., Luong, M., Le, Q., V., & Manning, C. D. (2020). ELECTRA: Pre-training text encoders as discriminators rather than generators. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2003.10555>
- [10] Wolf, T., Debut, L., Sanh, V., Chaumond, J., Delangue, C., Moi, A., Cistac, P., Rault, T., Louf, R., Funtowicz, M., & Brew, J. (2019). HuggingFace's Transformers: State-of-the-art natural language processing. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1910.03771>
- [11] Li, X., Feng, J., Meng, Y., Han, Q., Wu, F., & Li, J. (2019). A unified MRC framework for named entity recognition. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1910.11476>
- [12] Sun, C., Huang, L., & Qiu, X. (2019). Utilizing BERT for Aspect-Based sentiment analysis via constructing auxiliary sentence. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1903.09588>
- [13] Lee, J., Yoon, W., Kim, S., Kim, D., Kim, S., So, C. H., & Kang, J. (2019). BioBERT: a pre-trained biomedical language representation model for biomedical text mining. *Bioinformatics*, 36(4), 1234–1240. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz682>
- [14] Pires, T., Schlinger, E., & Garrette, D. (2019). How multilingual is Multilingual BERT? *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1906.01502>
- [15] Sanh, V., Debut, L., Chaumond, J., & Wolf, T. (2019). DistilBERT, a distilled version of BERT: smaller, faster, cheaper and lighter. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1910.01108>
- [16] Li, L., Ma, R., Guo, Q., Xue, X., & Qiu, X. (2020). BERT-ATTACK: Adversarial attack against BERT using BERT. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2004.09984>
- [17] Si, C., Zhang, Z., Qi, F., Liu, Z., Wang, Y., Liu, Q., & Sun, M. (2021). Better Robustness by More Coverage: Adversarial and Mixup Data Augmentation for Robust Finetuning. *Association for Computational Linguistics, Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: ACL-IJCNLP 2021*, 1569–1576. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2021.findings-acl.137>
- [18] Garg, S., & Ramakrishnan, G. (2020). BAE: BERT-based Adversarial Examples for Text Classification. *Association for Computational Linguistics, Proceedings of the 2020*

Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP), 6174–6181. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.emnlp-main.498>

[19] Fefferman, C., Mitter, S., & Narayanan, H. (2013). Testing the manifold hypothesis. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1310.0425>

[20] Goodfellow, I. J., Shlens, J., & Szegedy, C. (2014). Explaining and harnessing adversarial examples. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1412.6572>

[21] Papernot, N., McDaniel, P. D., & Goodfellow, I. J. (2016). Transferability in Machine Learning: from Phenomena to Black-Box Attacks using Adversarial Samples. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1605.07277>

[22] Alzantot, M., Sharma, Y., Elgohary, A., Ho, B., Srivastava, M., & Chang, K. (2018). Generating natural language adversarial examples. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1804.07998>

[23] Tsipras, D., Santurkar, S., Engstrom, L., Turner, A., & Madry, A. (2018). Robustness May Be at Odds with Accuracy. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1805.12152>

[24] Miyato, T., Maeda, S., Koyama, M., & Ishii, S. (2017). Virtual Adversarial Training: A Regularization Method for Supervised and Semi-Supervised Learning. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1704.03976>

[25] Zang, Y., Qi, F., Yang, C., Liu, Z., Zhang, M., Liu, Q., & Sun, M. (2020). Word-level Textual Adversarial Attacking as Combinatorial Optimization. *Association for Computational Linguistics, Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 6066–6080. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.540>

[26] Alfeld, S., Zhu, X., & Barford, P. (2016). Data Poisoning Attacks against Autoregressive Models. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 30(1). <https://doi.org/10.1609/aaai.v30i1.10237>

[27] Xue, M., Yuan, C., Wang, J., & Liu, W. (2020a). DPAEG: A Dependency Parse-Based Adversarial Examples Generation Method for Intelligent Q&A Robots. *Security and Communication Networks, 2020*, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/5890820>

Appendices

Appendix A – Attack Results Summaries

Table 6. BERT base model adversarial attack summary

Attack	EM	F1	BLUE	Av. GE	Sample Size
No Attack	6.91×10^{-5}	0.021	0.004	-0.094	86821
AddAny	0.000	0.034	0.006	1.432	67945
AddSent	1.47×10^{-5}	0.032	0.006	0.714	67945
CEIA	7.05×10^{-5}	0.028	0.004	0.711	56724
DPAEG	5.34×10^{-5}	0.028	0.004	0.701	56143
TextFooler	3.68×10^{-5}	0.027	0.004	0.787	54351

Table 7. BERT fine-tuned model adversarial attack summary

Attack	EM	F1	BLUE	Av. GE	Sample Size
No Attack	0.692	0.848	0.181	0.011	86821
AddAny	0.667	0.846	0.168	0.029	67945
AddSent	0.667	0.844	0.168	0.033	67945
CEIA	0.789	0.888	0.140	0.021	56724
DPAEG	0.635	0.733	0.111	0.032	56143
TextFooler	0.370	0.451	0.062	0.035	54351

Table 8. RoBERTa base model adversarial attack summary

Attack	EM	F1	BLUE	Av. GE	Sample Size
No Attack	1.15×10^{-5}	0.024	0.004	0.231	86821
AddAny	2.94×10^{-5}	0.032	0.006	0.796	67945
AddSent	1.47×10^{-5}	0.039	0.007	1.009	67945
CEIA	0.000	0.033	0.004	0.761	56724
DPAEG	1.78×10^{-5}	0.033	0.004	0.729	56143
TextFooler	1.84×10^{-5}	0.031	0.004	0.683	54351

Table 9. RoBERTa fine-tuned model adversarial attack summary

Attack	EM	F1	BLUE	Av. GE	Sample Size
No Attack	0.049	0.843	0.164	0.009	86821
AddAny	0.054	0.849	0.157	0.005	67945
AddSent	0.054	0.841	0.154	0.006	67945

CEIA	0.026	0.862	0.123	0.002	56724
DPAEG	0.022	0.738	0.102	0.007	56143
TextFooler	0.013	0.492	0.065	0.012	54351

Table 10. ELECTRA base model adversarial attack summary

Attack	EM	F1	BLUE	Av. GE	Sample Size
No Attack	0.000	0.035	0.006	1.247	86821
AddAny	1.47×10^{-5}	0.027	0.004	0.613	67945
AddSent	0.000	0.037	0.005	1.843	67945
CEIA	0.000	0.021	0.003	0.099	56724
DPAEG	1.78×10^{-5}	0.020	0.002	0.082	56143
TextFooler	0.000	0.020	0.002	0.146	54351

Table 11. ELECTRA fine-tuned model adversarial attack summary

Attack	EM	F1	BLUE	Av. GE	Sample Size
No Attack	0.812	0.895	0.229	0.027	86821
AddAny	0.081	0.888	0.213	0.038	67945
AddSent	0.805	0.884	0.211	0.037	67945
CEIA	0.902	0.919	0.172	0.030	56724
DPAEG	0.755	0.792	0.142	0.085	56143
TextFooler	0.466	0.530	0.085	0.019	54351

Appendix B – Key Visualizations

Figure 10. Exact Match Comparison for Each Model

Figure 11. F1 Score Comparison for Each Model

Figure 12. BLEU Score Comparison for Each Model

Figure 13. Attack Effectiveness Comparison for Each Attack by Exact Match
 (Lower score is best for attack success rate)

Figure 14. Attack Effectiveness Comparison for Each Attack by F1 Score
(Lower score is best for attack success rate)

Figure 15. Attack Success Rate Comparison for Each Attack by Model

Appendix C – Project Files (Codes & Datasets)

I had presented all project files except attack results files on GitHub:

<https://github.com/fesarikaya/AdversarialAttacks>

Result files on Google Drive:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1IGMRGW64eNGQqDIW2Za04jCzWnArRiXe>

Adversarial Attack Results

Attack result files can be seen under the **Attack/** directory for each model.

BERT-base: bert-base-uncased_adversarial_attack_results.csv

BERT-finetuned: bert-base-uncased-squad2_adversarial_attack_results.csv

RoBERTa-base: roberta_adversarial_attack_results.csv

RoBERTa-finetuned: roberta-base-squad2_adversarial_attack_results.csv

ELECTRA-base: electra_adversarial_attack_results.csv

ELECTRA-finetuned: electra-base-squad2_adversarial_attack_results.csv

Adversarial Attack Result Summaries

Attack result summary files can be seen under the **Summary/** directory for each model.

BERT-base: bert-base-uncased_adversarial_attack_summary.csv
BERT-finetuned: bert-base-uncased-finetuned-squad2_adversarial_attack_summary.csv
RoBERTa-base: roberta_adversarial_attack_summary.csv
RoBERTa-finetuned: roberta-base-squad2_adversarial_attack_summary.csv
ELECTRA-base: electra_adversarial_attack_summary.csv
ELECTRA-finetuned: electra-base-squad2_adversarial_attack_summary.csv

Adversarial Attack Notebooks

Attack Jupyter notebook files can be seen under the **main** directory for each model.

No Attack (Baseline): no_adversarial_attack_all_models.ipynb
BERT-base: adversarial_attack_to_bert-base-uncased.ipynb
BERT-finetuned: adversarial_attack_to_bert-base-uncased-squad2.ipynb
RoBERTa-base: adversarial_attack_to_roberta.ipynb
RoBERTa-finetuned: adversarial_attack_to_roberta-base-squad2.ipynb
ELECTRA-base: adversarial_attack_to_electra.ipynb
ELECTRA-finetuned: adversarial_attack_to_electra-base-squad2.ipynb

Adversarial Attack Datasets

Attack dataset json files can be seen under the **SQuAD** directory for each attack.

Baseline: train-v2.0.json
AddAny: squad-v2.0-addany.json
AddSent: squad-v2.0-addsent.json
CEIA: squad-v2.0-CEIA.json
DPAEG: squad-v2.0-dpaeg.json
TextFooler: squad-v2.0-textfooler.json

Adversarial Attack Dataset Generation Notebooks

Attack dataset generation Jupyter notebook files can be seen under the **main** directory for each attack.

AddAny: CreateAttackDataset_AddAny.ipynb
AddSent: CreateAttackDataset_AddSent.ipynb
CEIA: CreateAttackDataset_CEIA.ipynb
DPAEG: CreateAttackDataset_DPAEG.ipynb
TextFooler: CreateAttackDataset_TextFooler.ipynb

Evaluation Framework Notebook

Evaluation framework Jupyter notebook file can be seen under the **main** directory.

Notebook: AttackResultsAnalysis.ipynb

RoBERTa Specific Analysis Notebook

RoBERTa specific analysis Jupyter notebook file can be seen under the **main** directory.

Notebook: RoBERTa Analysis.ipynb

Architecture Diagram Files

Architecture diagrams was creating by using SVG (Scalable Vector Graphics). These files can be seen under the **main** directory for each architecture.

Transformer: transformer-architecture.svg

BERT: bert-architecture.svg

RoBERTa: roberta-architecture.svg

ELECTRA: electra-architecture.svg